

**THE LOSS IN PURCHASING POWER OF PUBLIC
EMPLOYEES DESPITE ADJUSTMENT IN
SALARIES TO INFLATION RATE:
A CASE OF TURKEY**

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Abstract

Inflation, which refers to a sustained and noticeable increase in the overall price levels within a country, erodes the real purchasing power of its citizens. Consequently, governments in countries experiencing high inflation typically strive to mitigate these losses by increasing nominal wages and salaries. This study highlights that, in environments with high inflation rates, particularly within the public sector, biannual salary increases do not fully offset the impact of inflation on purchasing power. Employing time value of money techniques in engineering economics, the study demonstrates that inflation raises are insufficient to fully restore purchasing power, and provides policy recommendations as a result. The unique and original nature of this study makes it a valuable contribution to the existing literature in this field.

Key words: Inflation, purchasing power, purchasing capacity, compensate of inflation

**ENFLASYONA GÖRE AYARLANAN MAAŞLARA RAĞMEN KAMU
ÇALIŞANLARININ SATIN ALMA GÜCÜNDEKİ KAYIP: TÜRKİYE
ÖRNEĞİ**

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Özet

Bir ülkede fiyatlar genel düzeyinin sürekli ve hissedilir bir şekilde artması anlamına gelen enflasyon, o ülke vatandaşlarının reel satın alma gücünü azaltır. Bu nedenle genel olarak yüksek enflasyona sahip ülkelerde hükümetler nominal ücretlere/maaşlara zam yaparak reel kayıpları önlemeyi amaçlar. Bu çalışma, yüksek enflasyonist bir ortamda özellikle kamu kesiminde yılda iki kez yapılan maaş artışlarının satın alma gücüne enflasyon oranı kadar yansımadağını ortaya koymaktadır. Çalışmada yöntem olarak mühendislik ekonomisindeki paranın zaman değeri ile ilgili teknikler uygulanmış, enflasyon zamlarının satın alma gücünü tam olarak telafi etmediği ortaya konmuş ve politika önerileri sunulmuştur. Bu itibarla çalışma, alanında tek ve özgün bir çalışma olarak literatüre katkı sağlamaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Enflasyon, sıfır enflasyon, satın alma gücü, satın alma gücü kapasitesi, enflasyonun telafisi

INTRODUCTION

Inflation is a term that refers to an abundance, bloating, and increase in the general level of prices. However, in economic literature, inflation is defined as continuous increases in the general level of prices. In some studies, it is observed that inflation is mistakenly used to mean a decrease in purchasing power. While this statement may be true for individuals with fixed incomes during times of inflation, such as those in certain trade sectors or speculators, inflation may lead to an increase in purchasing power, resulting in enrichment rather than impoverishment.

Although these can be said briefly for inflation, in fact, Wang et al (2022) point out in their article that this concept is not easy to explain simply and say the following. “Inflation has always been a hot topic studied by many scholars in the economic field. Many scholars have different ways of defining the phenomenon of inflation. Friedman (1968), as the leader of the monetarism school, explained inflation from the monetary aspect as a monetary phenomenon caused by excessive money supply. In addition, price school scholars emphasize the result of inflation and explain inflation as the process of the general price level rising continuously (Laidler and Parkin, 1977, s. 169–237). In the face of the complexity and uncertainty of inflation, scholars around the world have different discussions on the causes of inflation due to the differences in basic concepts and backgrounds. Different theories have been formed according to the influencing factors of inflation, including demand-pull theory, monetary theory, cost-push theory, structural theory, input theory, expectation theory and so on” (Wang et al, 2022)

The loss in purchasing power appears to be compensated when wages are increased by the rate of inflation. But there is no such increase in real terms. Workers initially rejoice at the rise in nominal wages, they later realize that their real wages have not increased. Since accurate price comparisons are difficult workers must tax their memories and powers of calculation to compare prices of goods at different periods of time (Gavin and Stockman, 1988). The inability of workers to understand the difference between nominal and real wages is included in the literature by I. Fisher in 1928 as the concept of "monetary illusion". Efe (2022) revealed in his study for Turkey between 2003 and 2022 that many public employees lost their real wages due to the monetary illusion.

In this study, it is revealed why the purchasing power and capacities of public employee have decreased and how they can be compensated, although it is stated that the salaries or wages of public employees are increased at the rate of inflation every six months. We make use of the graphical tools and formulas used in engineering economic while revealing the negative consequences of inflation that not easily noticeable. Although, in this work, we analyse the consequences of inflation in this study, the causes of inflation and how to reduce or eliminate it are beyond the scope of our study. However, the fact of inflation will be briefly mentioned, as the main theme of our study is to show the effect of inflation on the irrecoverable purchasing power losses of salaried public employees.

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1. SALARIES AND PURCHASING POWER IN THE ABSENCE OF INFLATION

Although an environment without inflation seems like a utopia, it can be considered as a target to be approached, just like the "zero defect" in the philosophy of total quality. While there are those who support the zero-inflation target, there are those who argue that zero inflation targeting is not an optimal approach. In our study, we will consider the zero-inflation situation as a reference point. For example, Neal advocates zero inflation in her article and says: "By eliminating inflation, we will establish the essential foundation for the highest sustainable levels of economic growth, employment, savings, capital formation, investment, productivity, competitiveness, and efficiency. We will greatly reduce the likelihood of future recessions, make our country more competitive in world trade, and improve the standard of living for everyone. All of our people will benefit; no one will lose" (Niel, 1992).

Figure 1. Graphical Display of Salaries and Product Prices in the Absence of Inflation

Note that the numbers indicate end of the respective months.

However, some authors like Lepetit (2022) shows in his article that no-inflationary situation is not optimal by saying that “I show that adding an over lapping generations structure to the canonical New Keynesian model can generate an optimal inflation rate that is significantly positive. In a baseline calibration of the model, the optimal inflation target is comprised between 0.8% and 3.2% in annual terms. In this framework, deviations from long-run price stability are optimal because the rate at which firms discount future profit lows naturally differs from the rate at which the planner discounts future utility flows. In the absence of inflation, which is important in terms of being a reference point even if it is not optimal, the increase in salaries and wages is in the form of giving a certain proportion of the increased national income under the name of welfare share. In fact, it is seen that there is no significant difference between the author who advocates zero annual inflation and the author who defends the thesis that the optimal value should be 0.8 on an annual basis, and therefore we believe that it would not be wrong to take the annual zero inflation as a reference. Figure 1 represents the situation where prices are constant and salaries and wages are increased biannually due to share of the increase in national income.

Figure 2. Increase in Purchasing Power After Six Months Due To Increase of National Income

2. SALARIES AND PURCHASING POWER WHEN INFLATION EXISTS

There has never been a situation where there is no inflation in Turkey. In an environment of inflation, salaries and wages are increased at the rate of inflation so that purchasing power does not decrease.

Figure 3 shows the prices of the selected goods and services at the end of the months and the salaries or wages are paid twice in a year. In the six-monthly increase in the salaries and wages of the public sector employees, the prices of the products and services at the end of the months within these six-month periods are based on the inflation rates based on the price increase compared to the prices of the products and services at the beginning of the relevant months. In other words, it is accepted that the prices at the beginning of the month come to the prices at the end of the month by leaps, that is, by shifting not by a gradual increasing. This kind of consideration and calculation is not correct and the main reason of the loss in the purchasing power and capacity of salary of public employee and workers.

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Figure 3. The Situation Where Salaries Are Paid Semi-Annually and Prices Are Continually Increasing

3. IN AN INFLATIONARY ENVIRONMENT THE LOSS OF PURCHASING POWER AND PURCHASING CAPACITY AND ITS COMPENSATION

Government officials consider the total inflation calculated from the inflation rates at the end of the months in order to compensate for the loss of purchasing power of public sector employees due to inflation. However, this kind of compensation is not a real compensation. Although such a salary and wage increases provide returns in the purchasing power of six months ago, it cannot compensate for the losses incurred during these six months. In reality, the prices of products and services continuously increase during in the month at regular or non-regular time intervals. These increases can be weekly, daily or even hourly depending on the products and services. In this section, we show with the help of Figure 4, what the real total purchasing power of salaried employee lost over six months and show how this real loss of purchasing power should be compensated.

Seeing the fact that the prices of products and services do not shift from the beginning of the month to the end of the month, but continually and accepting that this continually increase is linear, we write the followings, making use of Figure 4.

Figure 4. Losses in Purchasing Capacity Due to Continuously Decrease Purchasing Power.

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S: Salary (monthly income)

S(0): Salary in the beginning of first month

S(1): Salary at the end of first month

S(2): Salary at the end of second month

$S(0) = S(1) = S(2) = S(3) = S(4) = S(5) = S(6)$

i: Inflation rate at the end of month

I(1): Inflation rate at the end of the first month

P: Price of the product

P(0): Price in the beginning of first month.

$P(1)=P(0) \times (1+i(1))$: Price at the end of the first month.

$P(2)=P(1) \times (1+i(2))$

$P(3)=P(2) \times (1+i(3)) \dots \dots P(6)=P(5) \times (1+i(6))$

Equations can be written. If the “i” inflation values of each month are equal to each other, the basic formula $F=P \times (1+i)^n$, which is widely used in engineering economics, is obtained. F is the future value, P is the present value and “i” is the interest rate, inflation rate or discount rate.

PP: It is the Purchasing Power and it expresses the total amount that the monthly salary or wage can be obtained from the fictitious aggregate product and services under consideration and is expressed in units (such as kg, number, m, etc.).

$$PP = \frac{S}{P} \dots (1)$$

$PP(0) = \frac{S(0)}{P(0)}$: This is the purchasing power in the beginning of first month

PP (1), PP(2) ...PP (6): These are representing the purchasing power at the end of these months.

PC: The purchasing capacity is the sum of the purchasing power which can be called long-term purchasing power. We accept that the prices of products and services, which are taken as a basis for the calculation of inflation, increase continuously and linearly (Kg, number, etc.)

$TPC = \sum_{i=1}^6 PC(i)$; total purchasing capacity or total purchasing power for 6 months of the salary and wage earner.

Total purchasing capacity consists of the sum of 6 trapezoidal areas as shown in Figure 4, it is known that the area of a trapezoid is half of the sum of the lower and upper bases multiplied by the height of the trapezoid.

As can be seen in Figure 4, the lower and upper base lengths of these 6 trapezoids are;

PP(0), PP(1), PP(2), PP(3), PP(4), PP(5), PP(6)

The height is 1 unit. In this case, the total purchasing capacity or total purchasing power is:

$$TPC = PC(1) + PC(2) + PC(3) + PC(4) + PC(5) + PC(6)$$

$$TPC = \frac{PP(0)+PP(1)}{2} \times) + \frac{PP(1)+PP(2)}{2} \times) + \dots + \frac{PP(5)+PP(6)}{2} \times)$$

$$TPC = \frac{PP(0) + 2[PP(1) + PP(2) + \dots + PP(5)] + PP(6)}{2}$$

$$TPC = \frac{PP(0)}{2} + PP(1) + PP(2) + PP(3) + PP(4) + PP(5) + \frac{PP(6)}{2} \dots (2)$$

Table 1 : Additional Income To Be Paid After Each 6-Month Period To Compensate For The Loss In Purchasing Power Due To Inflation Caused By Paying Salaries Every 6 Months

Year2022 Months	End of month Inflations (i) %	Price of product (P) TL/ (Kg)	Purchasing power (PP) In unit (Kg) (for salary of 10000 TL/month)	Purchasing power (PP) In unit (Kg) (for salary of 15000 TL/month)	Purchasing power (PP) In unit (Kg) (for salary of 20000 TL/month)
Beginning of 1st month	-	100	100	150	200
1. End of month	11,10	111,10	90,009	135,013	180,018
2.	4,81	116,44	85,878	128,817	171,757
3.	5,46	122,80	81,432	122,148	162,864
4.	7,25	131,70	75,927	113,891	151,855
5.	2,98	135,63	73,730	110,595	147,460
6.	4,95	142,34	70,253	105,379	140,505
Total inflation at the end of six month	42,34				
Six month total PC (kg) in absence of inflation			600	900	1200

Six month total real Power Capacity PC (kg)		492,10		738,15		984,20
Six month total loss of Power Capacity PC (Kg)		107,89		161,84		215,79
Six month total loss of income (TL)		15358,4		23037,6		30716,8
Six month total loss of income in (%)		25,59		25,59		25,59
Year 2021						
Beginning of 7th month	-	100	100	150		200
7. End of month	1,80	101,80	98,232	147,348		196,464
8.	1,12	102,94	97,144	145,716		194,288
9.	1,25	104,23	95,945	143,917		191,889
10.	2,39	106,72	93,705	140,557		187,410
11.	3,51	110,46	90,527	135,791		181,055
12.	13,58	125,46	79,704	119,556		159,407
Total inflation at the end of six month	25,46					
Six month total PC (kg) in absence of inflation		600		900		1200
Six month total real Power Capacity PC (kg)		565,40		848,10		1130,80
Six month total loss of Power Capacity PC (Kg)		34,59		51,89		69,19
Six month total loss of income (TL)		4340,4		6510,8		8681,0
Six month total loss of income in (%)		7,23		7,23		7,23
Year2021						
Beginning of month	-	100	100	150		200
1. End of month	1,68	101,68	98,348	147,522		196,695
2.	0,91	102,61	97,461	146,191		194,922
3.	1,08	103,71	96,420	144,629		192,839
4.	1,68	105,46	94,826	142,240		189,653
5.	0,89	106,39	93,990	140,985		187,980
6.	1,94	108,46	92,201	138,30		184,402
Total inflation at the end of six month	8,45					

Six month total PC (kg) in absence of inflation	600	900	1200
Six month total real Power Capacity PC (kg)	577,14	865,71	1154,29
Six month total loss of Power Capacity PC (Kg)	22,85	34,28	45,70
Six month total loss of income (TL)	2478,802	3718,203	4957,604
Six month total loss of income in (%)	4,13	4,13	4,13

The main Formula (2) is obtained. To obtain the 6-month total purchasing capacity, or in other words, the total purchasing power, it must be subtracted from the $PP(0) \times 6$ value, which is the 6-month total purchase capacity without access. In this case;

$$\text{Loss in 6 Months Total Purchasing Power} = [PP(0) \times 6] - (6 \text{ Months Total Purchasing Capacity (TPC)}) \dots(3)$$

Example: Shown in Table 1 the six-month total loss of purchasing power for January-June of 2022 and other related values can be calculated by using Formula (2) and equations as shown below. There are 3 parameters used this formula. These are a) the monthly salary, b) the price of the product at the beginning of the first month and c) the end of monthly inflation.

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Here: We assume a) and b) parameter values ourselves, and get c) parameter values from The Central Bank of the Turkish Republic (TCMB, 2022).

$$S(0) = 10000 \text{ TL}$$

$$P(0) = 100 \text{ TL}$$

$$P(1) = 100 \times (1 + 0,1110) = 111,10 \text{ TL}$$

$$P(2) = 111,10 \times (1 + 0,0481) = 116,44 \text{ TL}$$

$$P(3) = 116,44 \times (1 + 0,0546) = 122,80 \text{ TL}$$

$$P(4) = 122,80 \times (1 + 0,0725) = 131,70$$

$$P(5) = 131,70 \times (1 + 0,0298) = 135,63$$

$$P(6) = 135,6 \times (1 + 0,0495) = 142,34 \text{ TL}$$

$$PP(0) = \frac{S(0)}{P(0)} = \frac{10000}{100} = 100 \text{ unit (Kg)}$$

$$PP(1) = \frac{S(1)}{P(1)} = \frac{10000}{111,10} = 90,009 \text{ unit (Kg)}$$

$$PP(2) = \frac{S(2)}{P(2)} = \frac{10000}{116,44} = 85,878 \text{ unit (Kg)}$$

$$PP(3) = \frac{S(3)}{P(3)} = \frac{10000}{122,80} = 81,432 \text{ unit (Kg)}$$

$$PP(4) = \frac{S(4)}{P(4)} = \frac{10000}{131,70} = 75,927 \text{ unit (Kg)}$$

$$PP(5) = \frac{S(5)}{P(5)} = \frac{10000}{135,63} = 73,730 \text{ unit (Kg)}$$

$$PP(6) = \frac{S(6)}{P(6)} = \frac{10000}{142,34} = 70,253 \text{ unit (Kg)}$$

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If these obtained values are substituted in the formula (2), the total purchasing power for January-June;

$$TPC = \frac{(100)}{2} + (90,009) + (85,878) + (81,432) + (75,927) + (73,730) + \frac{(70,253)}{2}$$

TPC = 492,10 kg is obtained shown in Table 1.

However, if there was no inflation in this January-June period, the amount of product that could be purchased (ideal total purchasing capacity or power): 100 kg x 6 = 600 kg. Therefore, there is 600 kg – 492,10 kg = 107,9 kg of not purchased product. Since the price at the end of the 6th month P(6) is 142,34 TL/kg, in order to compensate for this not purchased product, 142,34 TL /kg x 107,9 = 15358,48 TL should be added to the salaried employees as compensation for the loss of purchasing power in a total of six months.

CONCLUSION

The increase of fixed incomes receive every 6 months is equal to the total inflation that occurred within 6 months. With this increase, fixed income earners have the opportunity to buy the product they bought 6 months ago again. However, this is not a real compensation for purchasing power, and the monetary values of the total purchasing power lost within 6 months are shown in Table 1. As can be seen in the related table, the losses in this purchasing power decrease as inflation decreases.

In this study, we reveal where exactly the loss of purchasing power which is especially felt at high inflation rates and not easily noticed, come from, how much it is and how it should be compensated. While revealing this hidden loss of purchasing power, we consider the fact that the price increases are not monthly but weekly, daily and even hourly during the month. As a result, we emphasize that the raises of salaries of the employees will not be sufficient and therefore, that salaries and wages should be increased in the amounts as shown in the study.

In this study, we assumed that the price increases over the months are linear. In addition, similar studies can be modelled with different ways such as by using the Regression Analysis or Artificial Neural Network techniques on real data by making determinations for weekly, daily and hourly price increases within months.

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